

1 **Oncogenic Braf induces integration-related transcription.**

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7 A defined order of events that are an interchangeable sequence of processes that, regardless of
8 oncogenic stimulus, result in transformation has not yet been described. These processes include
9 oncogene activation, modulation of DNA repair processes (mismatch repair [MSH/MLH family genes],
10 BRCA-associated HR/NHEJ double strand break repair), homeobox activation and activation of other
11 nuclear factors without homeobox domains that appear important for transformation, nucleosome
12 remodeling involving Swi/Snf, SSX/SS18, Arid family chromatin machinery, and other events we and other
13 have described in relation to transformation including mobilization of the Xist-associated imprinting
14 system, transposase activity (PGBD, SETMAR and other factors with transposase function), mutagenic
15 processes associated with activity of APOBEC and molecules with cytidine deaminase function including
16 CDA and CDT1, transcriptional apparatus modulation involving TFAP2C, GATAD2A/B and other factors,
17 as well as transcriptional activity associated with integration (genome insertion events).

18 We describe here activation of integration-related transcription resulting from expression of oncogenic
19 Braf, including induction of SSBP2 and NOV.

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